

FAQ(FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS)

ABOUT THE TREATMENT OF SPIDER AND

VARICOSE VEINS:

Laser [veins treatment near me](#) has become a popular new way to improve the look of your legs by removing unsightly varicose and spider veins. Varicose veins are large, swollen blood vessels that usually develop in the legs and twist and turn through the skin. Spider veins are smaller, and are usually red and purple in color - but can appear on the legs and face.

If you've developed either of these, you may be a candidate for laser vein treatment. There are several **varicose vein treatments near me** options on the market, so it's important to do your research and be informed about each, as well as the basics of spider and varicose veins. The paragraphs below outline the most important questions you should ask your doctor:

What causes varicose veins and spider veins?

There are several factors that can contribute to the development of varicose and spider veins, including heredity, obesity, hormonal influences, the use of birth control pills, or a past history of blood clots.

Those who have an occupation that involves a lot of standing, such as teachers, hair stylists, and nurses may find themselves more apt to get spider or varicose veins. Finally, they can be

caused by previous vein surgery, exposure to UV rays, and trauma or injury to the skin. Consult a **vein specialist near me, Jericho** in the case of severe vein issues.

Besides the visual appearance, how else do these veins affect the body?

Those with varicose veins often experience aching or cramping in the legs. They might also experience restlessness, burning, tingling, tiredness, or heaviness in the same area. Such types of situations require **vein treatment Jericho**.

Women may experience worse pain during certain parts of their menstrual cycle or during pregnancy. Other more severe symptoms include swelling and darkening of the skin.

Are there complications that can come from having varicose veins?

The two main complications associated with varicose veins are ulcers and blood clots. Ulcers can form on the skin near varicose veins and are caused by long-term buildup in the tissue, which is caused by increased pressure of blood within those veins. These appear as a brown-colored spot on your skin before the ulcer develops, so make sure to check with your doctor if you see this spot.

The second main complication is a blood clot. When this occurs, the veins will become enlarged and the leg will swell considerably. If this happens, contact your doctor for varicose **vein treatment near me on the South Shore** immediately.

Are there home remedies for treating varicose and spider veins?

If you've just begun to experience symptoms or aren't a candidate for surgery, there are two well-known home [vein treatments Hamptons](#) you can try. The first is support stockings,

which are available above the knee, below the knee, and pantyhose style. These are especially useful if you experience pain or discomfort, and can be purchased from pharmacies and surgical supply stores.

The second thing you can do is make minor changes in your lifestyle, including daily walking, better skin hygiene, and weight loss (if needed).

What are the other vein treatment North Shore options?

Luckily, treatment options for spider and varicose veins don't mean a long recovery or even a hospital stay.

Laser treatment - Laser treatment uses pulsed light treatments to heat energy, which damages or destroys abnormal veins. This treatment is ideal for those who don't like needles but can cause discoloration of the skin, staining, bruising, swelling, or blister formation.

Sclerotherapy - This is used primarily for the removal of spider veins, and works by injecting a solution into the veins that cause them to close, thus encouraging blood to route through healthier veins. Although injections may be needed more than once, this treatment option is usually very effective if done correctly. Common side effects include skin color changes, swelling, and itching in the affected area.

Vein stripping - This removes one large vein through a series of small incisions and can be done as an outpatient procedure.

Catheter-assisted procedure - With this type of treatment, a catheter with a heated tip is inserted into a large vein. As it's pulled out, the heat destroys the vein and causes it to collapse and seal shut. It's the most suitable treatment for large varicose veins.

Ambulatory phlebectomy - This procedure removes smaller varicose veins through tiny skin punctures